

Report on promotion of FAIR data within Photon and Neutron RIs

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Abstract

FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data management practices are not necessarily widely understood or valued within the research community supported by ExPaNDS Photon and Neutron (PaN) facilities, and the benefits and implications of their adoption need to be promoted within the community. In this report, we describe the activities undertaken by ExPaNDS to promote FAIR data policies, tools, and practices within the communities associated with PaN facilities. Different stakeholder groups have different priorities and concerns, so we present the approaches undertaken for each community in order to be most effective. In particular, we targeted the following groups: senior facilities management; instrument scientists; other facilities staff involved in data and information management; user groups in science communities; and the wider Research Data Management (RDM) community. We describe the promotional activities undertaken across the project. We conclude with a discussion on the likely impact of the work of ExPaNDS Work Package 2 (WP2) on the wider ExPaNDS partner community.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
approx	approximately
BESSY II	Berliner Elektronenspeicherring-Gesellschaft für Synchrotronstrahlung II
CECAM	Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
DAPHNE	DAta for PHoton and Neutron Experiments
DAPHNE4NFDI	DAta for PHoton and Neutron Experiments for Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur / National Research Data Infrastructure
DESY	Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron
DLS	Diamond Light Source
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure Foundation
ELN	Electronic Laboratory Notebook
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ePIC	Persistent Identifiers for eResearch
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESRF	European Synchrotron Radiation Facility
ESUO	European Synchrotron and FEL User Organisation
ETH	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule/ Swiss Federal Institute of Technology

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ETH Lib4RI	Library for Research Institutes (within the ETH domain)
EU	European Union
ExPaNDS	European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Photon and Neutron Data Service
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GANIL	Large National Heavy Ion Accelerator Research Infrastructure
GdR APPEL	Groupeement de Recherche Accélérateurs Plasma Pompés par Lasers
HZB	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
HZDR	Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf
IBERGRID	Iberian Grid Infrastructure
IG	Interest Group
INFRAEOSC	Enabling an operational, open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem
IXS	Inelastic X-ray Scattering
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Lattice QCD	Lattice Quantum Chromodynamics
LEAPS	League of European Accelerator-based Photon Sources
LENS	League of Advanced European Neutron Sources
MADICES	Machine-Actionable Data Interoperability for Chemical Sciences
MX	Macromolecular Crystallography
n.d.	no date
n/a	not applicable
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur / National Research Data Infrastructure
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

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ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier (ID)
PaN	Photon and Neutron
PaNET	Photon and Neutron Experimental Techniques
PaNOSC	Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud
PID	Persistent Identifier
PSI	Paul Scherrer Institute
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RDMO	Research Data Management Organiser
RI	Research Infrastructure
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
SXNS	Surface X-ray and Neutron Scattering
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
UO	User Office
VUO	Virtual Unified Office
WIP	Work in Progress
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The benefits and requirements of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data, systematic data management and publication are still not widely understood and accepted within the wider scientific community of the ExPaNDS partners. Data and computing are often seen as secondary aspects, used to solve the immediate goal of extracting scientific results from the experimental data, and good management practices and data publication left to the computing groups within facilities. Necessary record keeping to support FAIR data practice can be seen as burdensome without immediate rewards, and in some cases, open science publication can be seen as a threat to scientific priority and reward.

As a consequence, the ExPaNDS project has included activities aimed at advocating the use of FAIR data practices to its research community. This has sought to explain the benefit of committing to FAIR data practices, emphasising the value to the experimental team itself as well as the longer term benefits to the science supported by the facility. This also explains the tools and processes necessary to support FAIR data, with the necessary additional actions which users and facilities staff would need to undertake, and how good design of those tools and practices can reduce the burden on users. Further, by using embargos, citations and rewards, users can maintain their scientific priority while allowing appropriate reuse.

In this report, we describe the activities undertaken by ExPaNDS to promote FAIR data policies, tools, and practices within the communities associated with Photon and Neutron (PaN) facilities. Different stakeholder groups have different priorities and concerns, so we present the approaches undertaken for each community in order to be most effective. In particular we targeted the following groups: senior facilities management; instrument scientists; other facilities staff involved in data and information management; user groups in science communities; and the wider Research Data Management (RDM) community.

The promotional work was centred within ExPaNDS Work Package 2 (WP2) although activities were undertaken across the project. There was close collaboration with WP6 for organising and promoting events and preparing material and with WP5 in preparing and delivering training material, while WP1 was particularly involved with interacting with senior management. The project also coordinated closely with sister European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) projects, particularly PaNOSC, FAIRsFAIR and the other INFRAEOSC-05b projects in the FAIR Synchronisation Task Force.

The final section of this deliverable seeks to assess the impact of the advocacy, and indeed, the impact of the whole FAIR framework on the facilities. An assessment of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for ExPaNDS WP2 of the significant actions undertaken by facility partners to enhance the FAIRness of their data management practices is given, demonstrating the wide range of actions which are being undertaken within facilities as a result of the project. These include:

- Introducing and developing data policies explicitly supporting FAIR data
- Introducing and developing support for Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) to support data publication and citation
- Review of metadata standards and methods used in data catalogues

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- Introduction of systematic data licencing
- Introducing the use of the Photon and Neutron Experimental Techniques (PaNET) Ontology to enhance data annotation
- Developing strategies to introduce Data Management Plans (DMPs).

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1. Introduction

The benefits and requirements of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data, systematic data management and publication are still not widely understood and accepted within the wider scientific community of the ExPaNDS partners. The community is understandably focussed on their immediate science goals, and on enhancing the capability of the facilities to perform more advanced experiments via upgrades to sources and instruments. Data and computing are often seen as secondary aspects, used to solve the immediate goal of extracting scientific results from the experimental data, and good management practices and data publication are left to the computing groups within facilities. Necessary record keeping to support FAIR data practice can be seen as burdensome without immediate rewards, and in some cases, open science publication can be seen as a threat to scientific priority and reward.

As a consequence, the ExPaNDS project has included activities aimed at advocating the use of FAIR data practices to its research community. This has sought to explain the benefit of committing to FAIR data practices, emphasising the value to the experimental team itself as well as the longer term benefits to the science supported by the facility. This would also explain the tools and processes necessary to support FAIR data, with the necessary additional actions which users and facilities staff would need to undertake, and how good design of those tools and practices can reduce the burden on users. Further, by using embargos, citations and rewards, users can maintain their scientific priority while allowing appropriate reuse.

WP2: Enabling FAIR data for PaN national RIs

Figure 1: Components of a Framework for ExPaNDS WP2 Key Advocacy Areas for Promoting FAIR in National PaN Research Infrastructures (RIs)

In this report, we describe the activities undertaken by ExPaNDS to promote FAIR data policies, tools, and practices within the communities associated with Photon and Neutron (PaN) facilities. Different stakeholder groups have different priorities and concerns, so we present the approaches undertaken for each community in order to be most effective. In particular, we targeted the following groups: senior facilities management; instrument scientists; other facilities staff involved in data and information management; user groups in science communities; and the wider Research Data Management (RDM) community. The work of ExPaNDS Work Package 2 (WP2) can be seen as developing a framework of recommendations for implementing FAIR policies and practices within PaN facilities, and we sought to extract and promote key messages from each as they were developed, as presented in Figure 1 above.

The promotional work was centred within WP2 although activities were undertaken across the project. There was close collaboration with WP6 for organising and promoting events and preparing material and with WP5 in preparing and delivering training material, while WP1 was particularly involved with interacting with senior management. The project also coordinated closely with sister European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) projects, particularly PaNOSC, FAIRsFAIR and the other INFRAEOSC-05b projects in the FAIR Synchronisation Task Force.

The final section this deliverable seeks to assess the impact of the advocacy, and indeed the impact of the whole FAIR framework on the facilities. This includes a review of significant actions undertaken by facility partners to enhance the FAIRness of their data management practices.

2. Stakeholder Map

The table below maps the various stakeholder groups we sought to reach with our FAIR advocacy to both the messaging/impact that we felt was important for those groups and to the specific promotion approaches we used to engage with the groups. The approaches (in column three) are discussed in more detail in the next section of this report.

Stakeholder Group	Desired Message	Approach
Facilities Senior Management	Importance and value of FAIR data practices. Setting policy for FAIR data practices Indication of likely investments and returns.	Deliverables, Other Internal Documents, Presentations, Workshops, Structured Discussions, FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force and INFRAEOSC-05b FAIR Task Force (i.e. through the ExPaNDS representation of PaN RIs and the PaN community in these forums)
Facilities Staff: Instrument Scientists	Importance and value of FAIR data practices being embedded throughout the PaN experimental lifecycle.	Deliverables, Other Internal Documents, Presentations, Workshops, Structured Discussions

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	<p>Consequences of implementing FAIR practices and mitigations on additional costs.</p> <p>The need to engage with users around FAIR, especially in relation to user-supplied sample and analysis metadata.</p>	
Facilities Staff: Data and computational support	<p>Importance and value of implementing FAIR data practices throughout PaN facility data collection, processing, storage, and analysis IT processes, workflows, and pipelines.</p> <p>Recognition that FAIR data policy needs to guide internal implementation practice.</p> <p>Implementation strategies for FAIR data.</p>	Deliverables, Other Internal Documents, Presentations, Workshops, Structured Discussions
Facilities Staff: Librarians	<p>What FAIR data looks like in the PaN context and how this data can be shared more widely via mappings to generic metadata standards.</p> <p>The need for FAIR practices to be supported by data librarians and stewards.</p> <p>The specific challenges for FAIR data faced in the PaN context around sample and analysis metadata and collecting data across the entire experimental lifecycle.</p>	Deliverables, Other Internal Documents, Presentations, Workshops, Structured Discussions
User Scientists	<p>Importance and value of FAIR data practices.</p> <p>In particular, the need for user-supplied sample and processing/analysis-stage metadata to support the reuse element of FAIR.</p>	Deliverables, Presentations, Workshops, Outreach Material

<p>Research Data Management Community</p>	<p>The nature of FAIR data practices in the PaN context.</p> <p>Role of PaN facilities in supporting scientific research within a wide range of scientific fields, so that it can be coordinated with FAIR practices in those domains.</p> <p>How these cross over with generic FAIR RDM, and where PaN context-specific FAIR RDM is required and what this looks like in practice, including in the EOSC.</p>	<p>Deliverables, Presentations, Outreach Material, FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force and INFRAEOSC-05b FAIR Task Force</p>
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Table 1: Mapping between Stakeholder Groups, FAIR Messaging, and Advocacy Approach

3. FAIR Promotion Activities to Address Stakeholders

The sections below overview the different types of advocacy activity we undertook in ExPaNDS to promote FAIR, which stakeholder groups we targeted, and how we matched activity type and stakeholder group to best convey our desired messages around FAIR (see Section 2 for details of these messages as they apply to each stakeholder group).

3.1 Deliverables

ExPaNDS WP2 has produced a total of nine formal project deliverables (i.e. including the present deliverable). These are listed in the Appendix by date.

While aimed particularly at the facilities-related stakeholders listed in Section 2, our deliverables will be of interest to all groups included in our stakeholder map. For example, PaN user scientists will find that the deliverables improve their understanding of metadata requirements, while the RDM community will be better placed to understand RDM in the PaN context as a result of these WP2 outputs.

The deliverables are also available to a wider public audience as open access documents via the ExPaNDS Zenodo community.¹ Indeed, the Zenodo view and download statistics provide some evidence that the ExPaNDS WP2 deliverables have attracted interest. In particular, our FAIR metadata framework set out in detail in Deliverable D2.2² and published

¹ See <https://zenodo.org/communities/expands/about/> .

² Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312825> .

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in December 2020 currently has the highest download statistic of all ExPaNDS deliverables (even compared with outputs published at a similar time or earlier).³ While download counts cannot definitively prove use, they are recognised as useful for providing some indication of the interest in a document, the rationale being that readers do not generally go to the trouble of downloading a document (i.e. as opposed to simply viewing it) unless they intend to return to that document later for some purpose.

3.2 Other Internal Documents

In addition to our formal project deliverables, WP2 felt there was a need to produce other documents intended primarily for internal project and PaN RI use. These documents are shorter in length than the formal deliverables and generally focus on practical elements (i.e. rather than literature reviews or theoretical concepts). They are designed to be used hands-on ‘at the coalface’ by facility staff and managers. Examples include our guidance note on data policy⁴ and our landscaping report⁵ produced early in the project. Both are included in the list of FAIR advocacy material compiled in the Appendix at the end of this report.

3.3 Presentations

Colleagues from WP2 and the other work packages have delivered a variety of presentations promoting FAIR over the course of the ExPaNDS project. These (see the Appendix) include standalone talks - for example, given at members’ own facilities or to a particular user community - as well as presentations given within the context of larger conferences.

Taken together, this presentation activity has addressed and reached the full range of stakeholders listed in our stakeholder map (see Section 2). In terms of numbers reached, as the examples listed in the Appendix indicate, there is huge variety (i.e. with numbers ranging from 32 to 185). However, it is notable that many of the presentations delivered by ExPaNDS members reached fairly large audiences of over 100 people.

Given that presentations by nature are often inherently quite limited in terms of the time allocated to speakers, our aim with our presentation activity in ExPaNDS has been to introduce and promote FAIR and related concepts at a relatively high level (i.e. rather than in

³ As of January 2023, ExPaNDS deliverable *D2.2 Draft recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management* has been downloaded 677 times since its publication in December 2020. (Notes: Download statistics extracted from zenodo on 26/01/2023. Data based on a search on the term ‘deliverable’ and the publication type set to ‘deliverable’ within the ExPaNDS zenodo community site. On the basis of this search, D2.2 had the highest download statistic of the 32 documents listed in the search results. Note that a limitation of this search approach is that any documents not containing the word ‘deliverable’ and not tagged as ‘deliverable’ would not appear in the search results. Also note that a wider limitation of using download statistics is that older outputs have inherently had more time to be downloaded. Bearing this limitation in mind, while we can currently say that D2.2 has the highest download statistic of the ExPaNDS deliverables, this may not remain the case in future, i.e. as time passes and newer deliverables have more time to accrue download counts.)

⁴ Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6090282>.

⁵ Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3673811>.

extensive detail as in our workshops, see Section 3.4 below). This aim was sensible given that FAIR was often still a newer concept for many of the stakeholders we sought to address.

3.4 Workshops

Over the course of the project, ExPaNDS WP2 facilitated a number of workshops, both within ExPaNDS and externally (e.g. RDA workshop). Our workshops were aimed at specific stakeholder groups (e.g. facility data managers and scientific computing staff, instrument scientists, librarians, user scientists) and offered the opportunity for more in depth exploration of FAIR-related topics such as PIDs, metadata, and FAIR-assessment.

Although a few were shorter, the workshops were normally a half or full day in length (i.e. comprising a morning and afternoon session) and sometimes spread across different days to allow more stakeholders to attend. The format we followed and that worked well for our stakeholders was to include multiple presentations (on a specific theme) followed by participant discussion. In any given workshop, we might facilitate several such one hour sessions designed to work together to form the total workshop. Some workshops also included specific sessions set aside for detailed and lengthy discussion (see Section 3.5 for further information).

While some of our workshops were purposely limited to a smaller number of attendees (e.g. 20-30) to allow for more intense interaction and discussion, others were designed to work well even with high numbers of attendees (e.g. 70-100). In all cases, our aim was to design and deliver workshops best suited to the needs and interests of the particular stakeholder group we were targeting. So, for example, our 'FAIR experiment' workshop was specifically aimed at instrument scientists and facilities computing staff to relay the message of how what they do (or don't do) influences heavily whether or not experimental data is FAIR. The Appendix provides further details on our range of workshops.

3.5 Structured Discussions

Structured discussions played a key role in maximising ExPaNDS WP2's engagement with stakeholders. An important strength of this activity was its focus on two-way conversation, which not only provided useful feedback to inform our work but also brought new ideas and issues to our attention that we might otherwise not have considered.

Semi-structured interviews (i.e. where we had a fixed set of seven framing questions but allowed the conversation around each question to go freely where it would) contributed significantly to the final version of our ExPaNDS data policy framework presented in Deliverable D2.3. We conducted these online interviews with all ten ExPaNDS partner facilities over a period of four months in spring 2021. Additionally, some partners submitted written comments to augment the verbal discussion. A variety of facility stakeholder groups participated, including senior management, User Office staff, IT and research data managers, data librarians, instrument scientists, and legal specialists. User scientists were not directly involved; however, it is important to emphasise that user needs are at the forefront of ExPaNDS partners' thinking, meaning that users will have had an indirect impact on the feedback, particularly through the instrument scientists who participated.

ExPaNDS WP2 also employed structured discussion sessions in some of our workshops, including the workshops focused on the FAIR metadata framework (where two out of the three one-hour workshop sessions were discussion-based) and FAIR assessment (where the second of the two workshops focused on discussion). Again, the stakeholders participating in this activity primarily represented facility-related groups, especially data and computational support staff. Another workshop that benefitted from structured discussion was our librarian symposium, which aimed to bring together facility librarians and data managers to share and exchange their knowledge and different perspectives on research data management.

3.6 Outreach Material

A key aim of our outreach material was to take FAIR advocacy in particular to the non-facility groups listed in our stakeholder map (see Section 2). These groups included PaN user scientists and the wider research data management community along with our sister project, PaNOSC, and other EOSC stakeholders. For the user scientist stakeholder group, we needed to bear in mind that user scientists are probably most interested in seeing the direct benefits of FAIR to their research (i.e. rather than the technical details of how to implement FAIR, for example). In contrast, the wider RDM community is likely to be very well-versed in FAIR implementation already, so what is of interest to this group is what FAIR RDM looks like in the PaN context and how that might differ from RDM in other communities.

The ExPaNDS FAIR outreach material is especially notable for its variety of format, ranging from journal articles to blog posts to videos. Our choice of format was first and foremost guided by what approach was most likely to speak best to the stakeholder group we were targeting. For example, the videos produced in ExPaNDS that comprise short interviews with ExPaNDS partner facility senior managers are intended to be easy for facility users to relate to, both in terms of content and delivery style. As well as our in-house activity, some of our ExPaNDS outreach material was developed through external collaborations, for example, as was the case with our FAIR implementation and adoption stories co-produced with the FAIRsFAIR project. The Appendix provides additional detail regarding our outreach material.

3.7 Working with Other Projects in the EOSC Programme

ExPaNDS has been active in FAIR advocacy as participants in formal task forces and through our links with other EOSC- and FAIR-related projects, including the ESFRI cluster projects⁶ and the INFRAEOSC-05 collaboration.⁷ Guided by a Joint Activity Plan, the INFRAEOSC-05 collaboration capitalised on the overlaps and complementary interests, including FAIR, across the FAIRsFAIR project, EOSCsecretariat, and the five INFRAEOSC-05b regional and thematic projects.⁸ ExPaNDS' formal participation in the related FAIR Task Force is discussed in more detail below.

⁶ These five cluster projects include: EOSC-Life, ENVRI-FAIR, ESCAPE, SSHOC, and PaNOSC. See <https://eosc-portal.eu/esfri-thematic-cluster-projects> .

⁷ See <https://eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/working-together-eosc-collaboration-agreement> .

⁸ The INFRAEOSC-05b regional projects include: EOSC-Nordic, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Synergy, and NI4OS-Europe. ExPaNDS is the only thematic project amongst the five INFRAEOSC-05b projects. See <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-regional-projects> .

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While ExPaNDS engaged with all of the ESFRI cluster projects, the relationship with our sister project, PaNOSC, was especially close, given that projects' similar focus on FAIR data and data services at PaN RIs and on the same user community. For example, ExPaNDS WP2 and PaNOSC WP2 benefitted from a shared interest and collaborative working in the areas of FAIR data policy and DMPs to support FAIR data.

Along with the ESFRI cluster projects and INFRAEOSC-05b projects, we also contributed across all three years of the FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force events (see the Appendix for details). These annual sessions, spread over several weeks, offered an excellent opportunity for ExPaNDS to share our work around FAIR and also to learn from and, where appropriate, to synchronise with the activity of other projects.

As mentioned above, ExPaNDS WP2 was an active member of the INFRAEOSC-05 FAIR Task Force. This task force brought together all of the '5b' projects, FAIRsFAIR, and EOSCsecretariat in regular formal meetings to share and discuss project outputs and work around FAIR. In addition to providing written progress updates to the Task Force, at each of the meetings, a couple of projects would normally present on some aspect of their current activity related to FAIR. For example, ExPaNDS WP2 gave presentations on its data policy and metadata frameworks. In this way, the INFRAEOSC-05 collaboration members could take new ideas back to their own projects and also keep abreast and informed about what related projects were doing.

As well as being important for the projects themselves, the activity of the FAIR Task Force was also of interest to the EC and EOSC stakeholders. For example, in November 2020, at the request of the EC, the Task Force held a special meeting, co-organised by EOSCsecretariat and FAIRsFAIR. The aim of this meeting was to report to the EC on work being carried by the collaboration member projects around the topic of FAIR data assessment and certification. This special meeting included a deep dive into use cases, discussion of the impact of FAIR assessment tools on research communities in Europe, and conversations about the priorities for the different stakeholders involved. The meeting content was subsequently captured in a formal report: FAIR Assessment and Certification in the EOSC Region (Dec 2020).⁹ We provide full details of this report in the Appendix.

4. Impact of Promotion Activities

Conducting activities to promote FAIR is one thing; generating impact from them is another. All the varied and carefully targeted activities outlined in Section 3 would be of no use if they made no impression on their audiences, or were soon neglected or discarded. In this section we show how the promotion activities have made a real impact on the stakeholders.

In the latest template for proposals under the Horizon Europe programme, *impacts* of a project are characterised as the wider scientific, economic and societal effects contributing to the overall destination of the work programme, while *outcomes* are changes seen after successful dissemination and exploitation of results. In this sense, what we can discuss in this deliverable is the outcomes that are already visible; nonetheless we can consider them as impacts because they will continue to shape the PaN landscape after the end of the ExPaNDS project.

⁹ Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4486280>

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A particular way of looking at impacts is in terms of KPIs. These are primarily intended to allow judgement on the progress of the project, since they make concrete the high-level objectives of the project in terms that can be measured. The ExPaNDS project took a very definite approach to its KPIs. The proposal and contract outlined specific judgements of success corresponding to the project's objectives, and how the necessary data would be collected. A task (6.3) was defined in the work plan for 'Formulation and dissemination of metrics and refinement of Key performance Indicators'. For WP2, the resulting KPI was: 'Number of facilities planning to implement at least one FAIR-related action as a direct effect of ExPaNDS', with a target of 10/10 (i.e. all the ExPaNDS partner facilities).

Table 2 presents the perceptions of the facilities themselves about the valuable impacts that have come directly from the project.

ExPaNDS Partner Facility	Planning to implement at least one FAIR-related action as a direct effect of ExPaNDS? (Yes/No)	Description and status of planned/ implementation
ALBA	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data policy (from 2017), update planned for 2023 • PID implementation: Alba member of DataCite from 2022 • ICAT in two beamlines, we need to update the metadata stored there • New section created for scientific data management in 2021
DESY	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PID implementation for data: requested by customer (PETRA III), generally considered by library - ONGOING • Metadata recording (and e-log-books) will be continued in the frame of DAPHNE4NFDI¹⁰
Diamond	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond is currently reviewing its data policy, pending Executive Committee approval with emphasis on FAIR principles • Diamond is part of the ORCID consortium • Review and use of Ontology

¹⁰ "DAPHNE4NFDI focuses on research with photons and neutrons at large-scale research facilities... The main goal of DAPHNE [Data from PHoton and Neutron Experiments] is "to make data from photon and neutron experiments "FAIR", thereby making scientific work more efficient and gaining more knowledge from the data." DAPHNE is one of the German NFDI (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur / National Research Data Infrastructure) consortia. See <https://www.daphne4nfdi.de/english/index.php> for more detail.

Elettra	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAIR-compliant data policy: improvement on the way: ready for approval by the President and Coordination Committee; • DOIs generated by most of the beamlines for raw data, for sure for the proposals; • Metadata are partially gathered in HDF + from VUO/proposal • DMP implementation WIP
HZB	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issue PIDs for raw data (implemented). We will use ePIC handles for this purpose. • Implemented PaNET in the metadata catalogue, We also contributed a script to populate the ICAT Technique table with the terms from PaNET.
HZDR	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update FAIR-compliant data policy (planned) • Metadata recording (and e-log-books) will be continued in the frame of DAPHNE4NFDI (in progress)
ISIS	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Already doing many of the FAIR criteria (PIDs, Data Repository, Access protocols Continuing with existing ones (API, Google dataset search) and two new methods added during the project - OAI-PMH and searchAPI- etc) • Revision of Data Policy. Introduction of Data Licencing to Data Policy. • Looking at the use of Ontology.
MAX IV	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOIs can be generated for data sets (using SciCAT). The service is in operation and has been tested (https://doi.maxiv.lu.se/)
PSI	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data policy updated in April 2022 • ELN deployed and rolled out to users in Autumn 2022 • OAI-PMH endpoint being harvested by B2FIND etc • PIDs for all datasets and DOIs for published data • DMP at facility and RI level training available, e.g. training event for ETH Lib4RI in November 2022. • Publications available in Google dataset search
SOLEIL	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOIs can be generated for UO/Proposals, In Progress for DataSets • Metadata for acquisition DataSets already gathered in Nexus Files • DMP implemented later

Table 2: Details of FAIR-related actions planned by ExPaNDS partners as a result of the project

Table 2 presents the facilities' perception of the impact of ExPaNDS on their own ways of working, for various internal stakeholder groups. The project has also made an impact in a

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larger arena and on broader groups of stakeholders, such as the general RDM Community. The following are highlights of this wider impact.

- In general, the project has raised awareness that the PaN community is an important actor in the RDM landscape. This is evidenced by the cooperative work with the FAIRsFAIR project, and the provision of an 'integrated use case' in photon and neutron science in the current FAIR-IMPACT project,¹¹ an important Horizon Europe project aiming to expand FAIR solutions across EOSC. This use case is on a par with the others in life sciences, social sciences/humanities and agri-food/environment.
- The ExPaNDS metadata framework is already showing strong influence both within and beyond the project partners (also mentioned in Section 3.1). The framework deliverable already has one of the highest download numbers of all the ExPaNDS outputs. It is something usable 'out of the box', ready to apply in practical situations for data and computing staff. Outside ExPaNDS, the German national DAPHNE4NFDI project is employing the framework.
- The two large European networks LEAPS¹² and LENS,¹³ together representing 28 PaN facilities, and which have a formal cooperation agreement, recognise the value of the work of ExPaNDS and intend to build on it. The LENS Initiative, for example, has a commitment to 'Achieve greater coherence in the development of data policy, data-handling, -storage, -analysis, -access along FAIR principles'.
- Looking specifically at EOSC, a concrete contribution has been made with the PaNET Ontology Service, available as a service through the EOSC Marketplace.

The impacts and activities discussed in this section give a basis for sustaining the results of ExPaNDS WP2. The details of the sustainability approach are out of scope of this deliverable on promotion activities, and will instead be covered in WP1 reports.

¹¹ See <https://www.fair-impact.eu/>.

¹² See <https://leaps-initiative.eu/>.

¹³ See <https://lens-initiative.org/>.

Appendix: Detailed List of ExPaNDS FAIR Promotional Activities

The table below lists by date and title the FAIR promotional activities undertaken by ExPaNDS WP2 and our project colleagues more widely. To facilitate easy links back to earlier sections in this deliverable, we include the type of activity (i.e. based on the activity types overviewed in Section 3) and the stakeholder audience (i.e. based on the stakeholder groups identified in Section 2). Additionally, we provide information about who led on/delivered the activity, and, where relevant, the number of attendees and any links to online material.

Date	Title	Activity	Lead ExPaNDS partner	Stakeholder audience	Number of attendees, if known	Link, if applicable
17/09/19	Fostering a FAIR research culture - what works?	Presentation (at workshop at Open Science FAIR, Porto, Portugal)	Brian Matthews, UKRI	Wider RDM community and ESFRI/5b EOSC projects	40	https://www.opensciencefair.eu/past-editions/2019/97-workshops/241-fostering-a-fair-research-culture-what-works
01/11/19	How FAIR can we be? FAIR data and facilities science	Presentation	Brian Matthews, UKRI	Diamond Light Source Facilities Staff	30	n/a
25/11/2019	First Synchronisation Workshop	FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force	UKRI	Wider RDM community and ESFRI/5b EOSC projects		https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/first-fairsfair-synchronisation-workshop

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19/12/19	ExPaNDS Data Landscaping Survey	Other Internal Documents	UKRI; PSI	ExPaNDS facilities staff and senior management	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3673811
29/04/20-11/06/20	Second Synchronisation Workshop	FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force	UKRI	Wider RDM community and ESFRI/5b EOSC projects		https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/fairsfair-2020-and-second-synchronisation-workshop
25/08/20	The ExPaNDS Data Policy Framework	INFRAEOSC-05 FAIR Task Force (presentation at Task Force meeting)	Abigail McBirnie, UKRI	Wider RDM community and 5b EOSC projects	7	n/a
18/09/20	D2.1 Draft extended data policy framework for Photon and Neutron RIs	Deliverable	UKRI	PaN facilities staff and senior management, wider RDM community	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014811
01/10/20	FAIR for facilities	Workshop	UKRI	ExPaNDS facilities staff	100	https://vimeo.com/493620481
02/10/20	The FAIR experiment	Workshop	UKRI	ExPaNDS facilities staff	70	https://vimeo.com/493767139

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02/11/20	Achieving a Photon and Neutron community federated cloud in EOSC: Enabling our facilities to produce FAIR data	Presentation (at EGI Workshop)	Brian Matthews, UKRI; with PaNOSC	Wider RDM community		n/a
09/11/20	FAIRsFAIR at FAIR for Facilities Workshop from ExPaNDS - A blogpost by Elizabeth Newbold	Outreach Material	Elizabeth Newbold, UKRI (with FAIRsFAIR)	Wider RDM community	n/a	https://www.fairsfair.eu/articles-publications/fairsfair-fair-facilities-workshop-expands-blogpost-elizabeth-newbold
26/11/2020	ExPaNDS	INFRAEOSC-05 FAIR Task Force (lighting talk at special Task Force meeting)	Sophie Servan, DESY	5b projects and wider RDM community, including EC and EOSC	15 (approx)	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1cgggPqn_s09TerLEphwGzQmtgCq0g4iDYTAXrsCQvmE/edit#gid=0
14/12/20	D2.2 Draft recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron data management	Deliverable	ALBA	PaN facilities staff and senior management, wider RDM community	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312825

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17/12/20	FAIR Assessment and Certification in the EOSC Region	INFRAEOSC-05 FAIR Task Force	Sophie Servan, DESY; Abigail McBirnie, UKRI	Wider RDM community, including EC and EOSC	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4486280
12/01/21	Invigorating the FAIR principles for surface science	Presentation (at SXNS16 conference)	Sophie Servan, DESY	Surface X-ray and neutron scattering scientists	70-80	<p>https://dlsitd.sharepoint.com/:p:/r/sites/GRA0046-PRV/Shared%20Documents/General/Meetings/2022-01-12%20ExPaNDS%20@SXNS16.odp?d=wb6b17aac13a14bb9b387b290689fe463&csf=1&web=1&e=4Gka0l (slides in .odp in Teams)</p> <p>https://dlsitd.sharepoint.com/:b:/r/sites/GRA0046-PRV/Shared%20Documents/General/Meetings/2022-01-12%20ExPaNDS%20@SXNS16.pdf?csf=1&web=1&e=kSNKHC (slides in .pdf in Teams)</p> <p>https://youtu.be/zMLjwpLZ-WQ (recording, from around 1:10:00)</p>
28/01/21	Best Practice Sharing Meeting - DOIs/PIDs for Datasets - Policy and Implementation	Workshop	Vasily Bunakov, UKRI; with additional content from ExPaNDS WP3 and	ExPaNDS partner facilities staff		<p>https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Z8jDMCDfq7NiPFnGPUPglqX1tEkaP_TtfPqq7iKNquU/edit?usp=sharing (post-workshop report)</p> <p>Presentation slides available on ExPaNDS sharepoint site (restricted access)</p>

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			PaNOSC Workshop report: Abigail McBirnie, UKRI			
Feb - May 2021	Data policy interviews with ExPaNDS partner facilities	Structured Discussions	UKRI	ExPaNDS facilities data and computing staff, senior management, instrument scientists	50 (approx)	https://dlsitd.sharepoint.com/sites/GRA0046-PRV/Shared%20Documents/Forms/AllItems.aspx?viewid=eaba4a75%2D52aa%2D4ee6%2D96ac%2Dd67a918eb891&id=%2Fsites%2FGRA0046%2DPRV%2FShared%20Documents%2FWP2%2FExPaNDS%2DData%2DPolicy%2DConsultations%2DAims%2Dand%2DFraming%2DQuestions%2Epdf&parent=%2Fsites%2FGRA0046%2DPRV%2FShared%20Documents (framing questions used for interviews - available on ExPaNDS SharePoint site, restricted access)
Mar 2021	RDA Facilities Data management and covid	Workshop	Brian Matthews, UKRI; Andy Gotz, ESRF	Research Data Management Community	40	n/a
30/03/21	Draft metadata framework for FAIR Photon and Neutron (PaN) data	INFRAEOSC-05 FAIR Task Force (presentation at Task Force meeting)	Abigail McBirnie, UKRI	Wider RDM community and 5b projects	13	n/a

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22/04/21	FAIR Data and Photon and Neutron Research Infrastructures (PaN RIs)	Presentation (at RDA Plenary 17, Breakout IG Session)	Abigail McBirnie, UKRI	Facilities staff, instrument scientists. User scientists. Wider RDM community		https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-17th-plenary-meeting https://www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-17th-plenary-meeting-programme#apr22 https://youtu.be/8KjEy_edECM
22/04/21	Research Data Needs of the Photon and Neutron Science Community: Sharing FAIR Data on COVID Research at Photon and Neutron Facilities	Workshop	UKRI; with PaNOSC	Facilities staff, instrument scientists. User scientists. Wider RDM community		https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-17th-plenary-meeting https://www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-17th-plenary-meeting-programme#apr22 https://youtu.be/8KjEy_edECM
29/04/21-10/06/20	Third Synchronisation Workshop	FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force	UKRI	Wider RDM community and ESFRI/5b EOSC projects		https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/fairsfair-event/fairsfair-third-synchronisation-force-workshop
10/06/21	FAIR RDM: Introduction to FAIR and research data management to support FAIR data	Presentation (as part of UK Catalysis Hub Data Management Workshop)	Abigail McBirnie, UKRI	UK Catalysis Hub staff, students, and researchers		https://youtu.be/yS_4xrvUPVk (presentation recording)
10/06/21	Reusing the FAIR	Presentation	Brian	UK Catalysis		https://youtu.be/3RcOKZ5fRcl

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	experiment	(as part of UK Catalysis Hub Data Management Workshop)	Matthews, UKRI	Hub staff, students, and researchers		(presentation recording)
29/06/21	ExPaNDS Develops a Data Policy Framework for National Photon & Neutron Research Infrastructures	Outreach Material	Abigail McBirnie, UKRI; with FAIRsFAIR	Wider RDM community	n/a	https://www.fairsfair.eu/news/expands-develops-data-policy-framework-national-photon-neutron-research-infrastructures https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5040078
20/08/21	D2.3 Final data policy framework for Photon and Neutron RIs	Deliverable	UKRI	PaN facilities staff and senior management, wider RDM community	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5205825
30/09/21	Symposium for librarians and data managers	Workshop	UKRI	Facilities librarians and data managers	70	https://vimeo.com/675857001 (morning session) https://vimeo.com/675860373 (afternoon session) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5973069 (workshop report and copies of presentations)

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22/10/21	Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for Facility Research	Workshop	Vasily Bunakov, UKRI; Rolf Krahl, HZB	Facilities staff and instrument scientists. User scientists, wider RDM community		https://vimeo.com/676015892 (recording) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6024624 (post-workshop report and presentation slides)
26/10/21	DOI, FAIR, and MX Covid-19 use case	Presentation (at 2nd PaNOSC and ExPaNDS PaN EOSC Symposium)	Frank von Delft, DLS	IT professionals, scientists and managers from the PaN community	120	https://vimeo.com/647369833 (recording) https://zenodo.org/record/5636331/files/20211026-PaN-EOSC-Symposium2021-Frank-vonDelft-DiamondMX-UseCase.pdf?download=1 (presentation slides)
15/11/21	Assessing the FAIRness of a prototypical PaN instrument at BESSY II	Presentation	HZB	Facilities staff and instrument scientists. Wider FAIR assessment community.		https://vimeo.com/647450948 (recording) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6059994 (presentation slides)
30/11/21	D2.4 DMPs for Photon and Neutron RIs	Deliverable	HZB	Facilities staff and instrument scientists. User scientists, wider RDM community	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5636096
07/12/21	ISIS Neutron and Muon Source -	Presentation	Alejandra Gonzalez-	ExPaNDS partner	15	https://agbeltran.github.io/talks/2021-12-

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	Scientific Data Management		Beltran, UKRI	facilities staff		07-ExPaNDS-WP3 (details) https://indico.maxiv.lu.se/event/5012/ timetable/#20211207 (timetable) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5841304 (slides)
20/01/22	ExPaNDS: Bringing FAIR photon and neutron data to the European Open Science Cloud	Presentation	Abigail McBirnie, UKRI	STFC (including ISIS) and Diamond staff; presentation also available to wider public	40	https://ukri.mediasite.com/mediasite/Showcase/opensciencecafe/Presentation/0af04e37dd704410b1fd760eca770c861d/Channel/75eb0342db6543f886595d14cd5aa8a55f
03/02/22	The role of Helmholtz Partners in FAIR related Photon and Neutron EU Projects	Presentation	Sophie Servan, DESY	Open science professionals of the Helmholtz Association (Germany)	185	https://doi.org/10.48440/os.helmholtz.044 (slides on pages 138-158)
07/02/22	Towards FAIR research data management	Presentation (at CECAM workshop on	Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran, UKRI	User scientists, the wider RDM community		https://agbeltran.github.io/talks/2022-02-07-CECAM-MADICES

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		“Machine actionable data for chemical sciences: Bridging experiments, simulations, and machine learning for spectral data” (MADICES))				
15/02/22	ExPaNDS Guidance Note: Key Policy Elements within a Photon and Neutron Research Infrastructure Data Policy Framework (revised - final version)	Other Internal Document	UKRI	Facilities staff and senior management. Wider RDM community.	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6090282
23/02/22	Data policy framework for photon and neutron research infrastructures	Outreach Material	Abigail McBirnie, UKRI; Simon Lambert, UKRI; with FAIRsFAIR	Wider RDM community	n/a	https://www.fairsfair.eu/implementation-a doption-stories/data-policy-framework-photon-and-neutron-research-infrastructure s-0 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6244742
02/03/22	FAIR metadata	Workshop	Nicolas Soler,	ExPaNDS facilities RDM		https://vimeo.com/685211186

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	for PaN RIs		ALBA; Abigail McBirnie, UKRI	and scientific computing staff		
03/03/22	D2.5 Advanced infrastructure for PIDs in Photon and Neutron RIs	Deliverable	UKRI	Facilities staff, instrument scientists, librarians. Wider RDM community	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5905351
05/04/22	Science des Photons et des Neutrons et EOSC : PaNOSC et ExPaNDS	Presentation (at EOSC-France 2022 Days)	Brigitte Gagey, SOLEIL	Delegates from French research organisations	145	https://eoscfrence2022.sciencesconf.org/399277 (presentation slides, in French)
11/05/22	SOLEIL et Science Ouverte	Presentation (Flash presentation, given as intro to a Round Table at the General Assembly of the GDR APPEL (Research Group on Laser Pumped Accelerators))	Brigitte Gagey, SOLEIL	Researchers, technical staff, experimenters and theoreticians in the fields of laser plasma acceleration and conventional accelerators	50 (approx)	https://indico.ijclab.in2p3.fr/event/8018/contributions/25687/attachments/18951/25583/OpenScience-at-SOLEIL-20220511.pdf (presentation slides, in French)
06/07/22	ExPaNDS FAIR Self-assessment	Workshop	Abigail McBirnie,	ExPaNDS partner		n/a

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	Workshop		UKRI; Simon Lambert, UKRI	facilities staff		
07/07/22	D2.7 Final recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron data management	Deliverable	ALBA	PaN facilities staff and senior management, wider RDM community	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6821676
26/08/22	ExPaNDS - Towards FAIR and open photon and neutron data	Presentation (at 12th International Conference on Inelastic X-ray Scattering IXS 2022)	Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran, UKRI	Facility instrument scientists, user scientists		n/a
29-30/08/22	What the ExPaNDS project provides as tools promoting FAIR open data sources and data analysis services for Photon and Neutron facilities	Presentation (at 18 th ESUO General Assembly)	Majid Ounsy, SOLEIL	Members of the European Synchrotron and FEL User Organisation (EUSO)	32 (representing 27 out of 31 EUSO member countries)	https://www.esuo.eu/18th-and-2022-annual-meeting-of-the-european-synchrotron-and-fel-user-organisation/
18-23/09/22	Challenges towards Open	Presentation	Patrick Fuhrmann,	Lattice QCD (Europe),	50 (approx)	https://indico.ifca.es/event/2452/contribut

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	Data in science		DESY	Management and Students		ions/12495/
21/09/22	Metadata framework for FAIR Photon and Neutron (PaN) data	Presentation	Heike Görzig, HZB	DAPHNE Project Task 1	25	n/a
21/09/22	ExPaNDS - Advanced infrastructure for PIDs in Photon and Neutron RIs	Presentation	Heike Görzig, HZB; Rolf Krahl, HZB	DAPHNE project Task 1	25	n/a
26/09/22	Reporting on the ExPaNDS FAIR Self-Assessment (follow on workshop)	Workshop	Abigail McBirnie, UKRI; Simon Lambert, UKRI	ExPaNDS partner facilities staff		n/a
10-13/10/22	FAIR data in the Photon and Neutron community	Presentation	Patrick Fuhrmann, DESY	Members of IBERGRID, Representative of the EC and (H2020) EOSC-Synergy team	70 (approx)	https://indico.lip.pt/event/1249/contributions/4433/
17/10/22	Open Science and Data at	Presentation	Brigitte Gagey,	Users and staff of the GANIL	152	https://gcm2022.sciencesconf.org/data/pages/OpenScience_Data_at_SOLEIL_B

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	SOLEIL	(at the GANIL Community Meeting 2022)	SOLEIL	(Large National Heavy Ion Accelerator) Research Infrastructure		GAGEY_202210117.pdf (presentation slides)
04/11/22	<p>HZDR Data Management Day (included 4 lectures addressing FAIR)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Overview of the Data Management Ecosystem at HZDR 2. Creating a Data Management Plan with RDMO 3. Data Management - Updates from the Library 4. Bridging Experiments and Bits 	Presentations	Uwe Konrad, HZDR; Oliver Knodel, HZDR	HZDR Staff	100	https://www.hzdr.de/db/Cms?pOid=67367&pNid=5
21/11/22	Research Data Management – The Basics	Outreach Material	Carlo Minotti, PSI	ETH domain students and employees	20	https://www.lib4ri.ch/files/2022-nov-rdm-p-si-web_1.pdf

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15/12/22	A Framework for Active DMPs in Photon and Neutron Science Large Scale Facilities (submitted to CODATA Data Science Journal)	Outreach Material	Heike Görzig, HZB; PaNOSC	User scientists and wider RDM community	n/a	https://datascience.codata.org/ (Call for Papers: Data Management Planning across Disciplines and Infrastructures)
19/12/22	D2.6 Self-evaluation Photon and Neutron RIs for FAIR data certification	Deliverable	UKRI	Facilities staff and senior management. Wider RDM community	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7246802
21/12/22	D2.8 Active DMPs for Photon and Neutron RIs	Deliverable	HZB	Facilities staff and instrument scientists. User scientists, wider RDM community	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7223438
24/01/23	Follow a user story: FAIR journey	Presentation (as part of the ExPaNDS Closing Event open session)	Brian Matthews, UKRI	Facilities staff and instrument scientists. User scientists, wider RDM community		https://indico.desy.de/event/36892/sessions/14452/#20230124 (session details)
Feb 2023	D2.9 Report on promotion of FAIR data within Photon and	Deliverable	UKRI	ExPaNDS partner facilities and project	n/a	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7572045

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	Neutron RIs			members, wider RDM community		
n.d.	The Benefits of Open Data	Outreach Material	DLS	User scientists and wider RDM community	n/a	https://player.vimeo.com/video/413955737
n.d.	What We Want to Achieve	Outreach Material	DLS	User scientists and wider RDM community	n/a	https://vimeo.com/405782505
n.d.	ExPaNDS - Making Data Available	Outreach Material	DLS	User scientists and wider RDM community	n/a	https://player.vimeo.com/video/637958452
n.d.	Inclusivity - Professor Roger Eccleston	Outreach Material	DLS	User scientists and wider RDM community	n/a	https://vimeo.com/781489872

Table 3: List of ExPaNDS FAIR Promotion and Advocacy Activities

Abbreviations used in table: n.d. (no date); n/a (not applicable). ExPaNDS partner facilities abbreviations (Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY), Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR), Diamond Light Source (DLS), Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB), UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), ISIS Neutron and Muon Source (ISIS)). Details explaining the other abbreviations used here are included in the 'abbreviations and acronyms' list found at the beginning of this report.

Where an element is left blank, no data is available.

